

SIGNIFICANCE OF BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE IN MEDICINE

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Abstract: This article talks about the biological laws that are of equal interest to everyone today and their importance in human life.

Key words: Medicine, pathogen, hereditary diseases, genetics, homeostasis.

Introduction: In the past, general problems such as the preservation of human health, food supply and preservation of the diversity of organisms on our planet, research aimed at solving these and other problems, biology, medicine, agriculture, industry, in particular, he could not worry about food and other things. Because mother nature gave all the blessings. However, the active and often ill-conceived economic activity of man has led to significant pollution of the environment with substances harmful to all living beings, destruction of forests, steppes and reservoirs.

Over the past centuries, thousands of species of animals, plants and fungi have become extinct, and tens of thousands of species are on the verge of extinction. But the extinction of a single species of organisms represents an irreversible loss for the biological diversity of our planet. Therefore, scientists compile a list (called Red Books) of plant, animal and fungal species that need protection. Thus, through its research, biology is a science called to convince people of the need to respect nature and obey its laws. Therefore, it is considered the science of the future. It is difficult to overestimate the role of biology in modern reality, because it studies human life in detail in all its aspects. Today, this science combines important concepts such as evolution, cell theory, genetics, homeostasis, and energy. Its tasks include the study of the development of all living things, that is: the structure of organisms, their behavior, as well as their relationship with the environment.

Today, many important and independent sciences separated from biology are known. These include zoology, botany, microbiology and virology. It is difficult to single out the most important of them, they all represent the most valuable set of fundamental knowledge accumulated by civilization. Claudius Galen, Hippocrates, Carl Linnaeus, Charles Darwin, Alexander Oparin, Ilya Mechnikov enriched the field of biology with clear evidence. Their discoveries, especially the study of living organisms, gave rise to the science of morphology, as well as the science of physiology, which includes knowledge about the systems of living organisms. Genetics played an invaluable role in the development of hereditary diseases. With the development of the science of genetics, several innovations were created in the history of mankind.

Importance of biology in medicine. An important role in the field of biology is to provide food for mankind. Scientists are creating new, high-yielding plant varieties and animal breeds that provide more nutrition. Living organisms are widely used in the maintenance and increase of soil fertility, which provides a high yield for biological research. They are also used in industry. For example, a person gets yogurt, kefir, cheese due to the activity of certain types of bacteria and fungi. Yeast fungi are widely used in baking. Biology has become a solid foundation in medicine, sociology, and ecology. Importantly, this science is not static like

other sciences, but is constantly filled with new knowledge and changes in the form of new biological theories and laws, but this is invaluable in medicine. It was with his help that methods of treating bacteriological and rapidly spreading viral diseases were found. Every time we think about the question of the role of biology in modern society, it is precisely because of the heroism of medical biologists that infectious epidemics: cholera, typhus, and anthrax have disappeared from the planet. Many medicinal substances are also obtained from plants or products of the vital activity of microorganisms. For example, the use of antibiotics (Greek anti - protve - and bios).

They are produced by certain types of fungi and bacteria. Antibiotics kill the pathogens of many dangerous diseases of humans and animals.

Based on the facts, it can be said with confidence that the role of biology in modern society is constantly growing. Modern life cannot be imagined without breeding, genetic research, production of new food products, as well as sustainable sources of energy.

The main importance of biology is that it serves as the foundation and theoretical framework for many promising sciences, such as genetic engineering and bionics. He has an amazing discovery - decoding the human genome. A field like biotechnology was created on the basis of the combined knowledge in biology. Currently, it is this nature of technology that makes it possible to create safe drugs that do not harm the body for prevention and treatment. As a result, it is possible to increase not only the length of life, but also its quality. The science of bionics means creating new techniques based on biological factors. The role of biology in modern society means that there are fields where its knowledge is simply necessary, for example, the pharmaceutical industry, gerontology, forensic medicine, agriculture, construction and space research. Today, it is difficult to imagine our life without the above areas.

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